

WHO
Strategic Advisory Group
on Malaria Eradication

Working papers

Group 7: Mitigating potential threats to malaria eradication

Title

Simian malaria: report on actions needed to mitigate threat of simian malaria on the road towards malaria eradication

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This working paper was commissioned by the WHO Strategic Advisory Group on Malaria Eradication between 2016 and 2019.

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World Health Organization Strategic Advisory Group for Malaria Eradication

Simian malaria:

Report on actions needed to mitigate threat of simian malaria on the road towards malaria eradication

by

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Summary

The vast majority of human malaria cases are caused by four parasites—*Plasmodium falciparum*, *P. vivax*, *P. malariae*, and *P. ovale*—but these species constitute less than 1% of the malaria parasite diversity found in the natural world. The expansion of human populations into biodiversity hotspots has elevated exposure to primate malaria parasites, a subset of which do possess the capacity to circumvent barriers to human infection. Although primate-to-human transmission is relatively rare, several emerging trends suggest that zoonotic malaria parasites may hold the potential to undermine future malaria eradication efforts. The incidence of *P. knowlesi* is increasing in Southeast Asia and is now the primary cause of malaria in parts of rural Malaysia. In Brazil, zoonotic *P. simium* outbreaks have recently been described in regions where elimination had been achieved for over 50 years. In equatorial Africa, ape-to-human transmission of *P. vivax* has been identified in the Central African Republic, suggesting that chimpanzees and gorillas may constitute an underappreciated reservoir of *P. vivax*, *P. malariae*, and *P. ovale* infections. This emerging body of evidence has established a public health imperative to critically evaluate the threat that these zoonotic malaria parasites pose to malaria elimination.

The purpose of this report is to highlight the challenges that primate malaria parasites pose to malaria eradication and to propose a series of steps that should be taken to mitigate this threat. The report proposes a holistic view of malaria zoonosis that simultaneously considers both ecological and molecular barriers to emergence. This approach will enable stakeholders in the scientific and public health communities to identify primate malaria parasites that pose a threat to human populations, quantify the magnitude and geographic distribution of this threat, and develop targeted strategies to most efficiently mitigate the threat.

First, it will be necessary to invest in basic scientific research that critically evaluates the ecological, epidemiological, and molecular drivers of primate malaria zoonoses. Doing so will facilitate the identification of exactly which parasites pose a tangible threat to human populations, where these parasites are distributed, and when seasonal cases are most likely to occur. To elucidate these topics, we must (1) identify foci of human exposure to zoonotic parasites, (2) evaluate the frequency of primate-to-human transmission, and (3) discern evidence of simian parasite adaptation to the human host.

Second, we must seek to mitigate the threat that primate malaria parasites pose to eradication efforts. In particular, two zoonotic systems offer important case studies: the macaque parasite, *P. knowlesi* (peninsular Malaysia and Borneo), and the New World monkey parasite, *P. simium* (Atlantic Forest region, Brazil). To combat these and other emerging threats, it will be important to invest in activities that (1) improve the diagnosis of simian malaria parasites, (2) evaluate the efficacy of current malaria therapies when applied to simian malaria parasites, (3) intensify control activities in zoonotic foci to reduce the risk of human-to-human transmission, and (4) promote advocacy and education to raise awareness among stakeholders ranging from public health officials to local populations impacted by these pathogens.

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Background

*Note: this section was adapted from a report written by Erik J. Scully for the WHO Strategic Advisory Group for Malaria Eradication (2017), titled “Non-human primate reservoirs of zoonotic malaria infection: an under-appreciated barrier to malaria eradication?”*¹

The vast majority of human malaria cases are caused by four parasites—*Plasmodium falciparum*, *P. vivax*, *P. malariae*, and *P. ovale*²—but these species constitute less than 1% of the malaria parasite diversity found in the natural world. Over 500 malaria parasites have been isolated from avian, reptilian, and mammalian hosts³, many of which are incapable of replicating in humans. However, the expansion of human populations into biodiversity hotspots has elevated exposure to novel malaria parasites, a subset of which do possess the capacity to circumvent barriers to human infection. This paradigm is underscored by the growing health burden posed by *P. knowlesi*, a parasite of macaque monkeys, which now constitutes the primary cause of malaria in parts of Southeast Asia^{4,5}.

Recent advances in molecular diagnostics and expanded sampling of wild primate populations have revealed that *P. knowlesi* is not the only malaria parasite to transcend species boundaries (**Figure 1**). The ancient origins of both *P. falciparum*^{6,7} and *P. vivax*^{8,9}—pandemic malaria parasites, which cause the majority of human malaria infections globally^{2,10}—have been traced to African great apes (i.e., chimpanzees and gorillas). *Plasmodium malariae* and *P. ovale* have also been isolated from African great ape hosts, though the directionality of transmission (i.e., ape-to-human or human-to-ape) remains unclear^{6,11–13}. Given the taxonomic diversity of malaria hosts, the observation that most (if not all) human malaria parasites originated in our closest evolutionary relatives is striking and has compelled the scientific and public health communities to ask whether primate reservoirs could impede malaria control efforts by acting as a source of recurrent human infection^{14–19}.

While these findings demonstrate that primate malaria parasites possess the capacity to emerge in human populations on evolutionary timescales, the threat that these pathogens pose to contemporary public health is less clear. Primate-to-human transmission is relatively rare, and most primate malaria parasites must overcome substantial barriers to infect human hosts²⁰. However, several emerging trends suggest that zoonotic malaria parasites may hold the potential to undermine future malaria control efforts. The incidence of *P. knowlesi* is increasing in Southeast Asia and now accounts for over 70% of malaria cases in parts of rural Malaysia^{4,5,17,21}. This country has also recently begun to witness zoonotic malaria outbreaks caused by another parasite of macaque monkeys—*P. cynomolgi*^{22,23}. In South America, zoonotic *P. simium* outbreaks have recently been described in areas of Brazil where regional elimination had been achieved for over 50 years²⁴. Monkey-to-human transmission of *P. brasilianum* has also been documented²⁵. In equatorial Africa, ape-to-human transmission of *P. vivax* has been identified in the Central African Republic, suggesting that chimpanzees and gorillas may constitute an underappreciated reservoir of *P. vivax*, *P. malariae*, and *P. ovale* infections. This emerging body of evidence has established a public health imperative to critically evaluate the threat that these zoonotic malaria parasites pose to malaria elimination.

Figure 1 | Evolutionary relationships of primate malaria parasites. Lineages are colored corresponding to geographic origin of host species (blue=South America; green=Africa; orange=Asia). Human-adapted lineages, which are globally distributed, are colored red. Lineages are labeled according to host species and degree of specificity for the human host in natural settings. Figure adapted from Scully et al.²⁰.

The purpose of this report is to highlight the challenges that primate malaria parasites pose to malaria eradication and to propose a series of steps that should be taken to mitigate this threat. To achieve this goal, this report proposes a holistic view of malaria zoonosis that simultaneously considers both ecological and molecular barriers to emergence. This approach should enable stakeholders in the scientific and public health communities to (1) identify particular primate malaria parasites that pose a tangible threat to human populations, (2) quantify the magnitude and geographic distribution of this threat, and (3) develop targeted strategies to most efficiently mitigate the threat.

Zoonotic disease emergence: an evolutionary process

The process of zoonotic disease emergence can be conceptualized as an adaptive continuum, whereby parasites are classified into one of three stages: parasites transmissible within the animal reservoir (Stage 1), parasites transmissible from animal to human (Stage 2), and parasites transmissible among humans (Stage 3)²⁶⁻²⁸. The natural diversity of primate malaria parasites spans the zoonotic spectrum (**Figure 2**).

A pathogen's position along the zoonotic spectrum is determined by its basic reproductive number (i.e., R_0) in the human host²⁶. R_0 is defined as the average number of secondary cases that arise from an initial primary case in a wholly susceptible population²⁹. More simply, the R_0 value describes a pathogen's capacity to persist within the host population and is a representation of the rate of transmission relative to the rate of recovery. If R_0 is less than one, the pathogen is incapable of sustained transmission within the human population and will eventually go extinct therein. By contrast, if R_0 is greater than one, the pathogen will emerge in the human population, yielding a sustained epidemic.

Many zoonotic spillover events are either incapable of forward transmission ($R_0=0$, or Stage 1) or produce stuttering transmission chains that eventually burn out in the human population ($R_0<1$, or Stage 2). Two parameters ultimately dictate a parasite's capacity to transition from Stage 1 to Stage 2: (1) the magnitude of human exposure to the novel parasite, and (2) the probability of human infection per exposure event. Discrimination between these two classes of barriers is a critical step in the evaluation of the risk that a particular parasite poses to the human population. Generally, factors that elevate human exposure to parasites that display a degree of affinity for the human cellular environment will influence the potential for cross-species transmission.

Subsequent parasite adaptation may permit efficient replication in the human host or elevate the rate of transmission within the human host population, yielding an evolutionary host shift ($R_0>1$, or Stage 3). Adaptations that facilitate parasite growth in the human cellular environment or elevate the rate of human-to-human transmission define a pathogen's transition from Stage 2 to Stage 3 by amplifying its R_0 value. Such adaptations hold the potential to transform low-impact zoonotic spillover events into human-adapted pathogens with pandemic potential.

Figure 2 | The zoonotic spectrum. The process of zoonotic disease emergence is typically conceptualized as an adaptive continuum, whereby parasites are classified into one of three stages: parasites transmissible within the animal reservoir (Stage 1), parasites transmissible from animal to human (Stage 2), and parasites transmissible among humans (Stage 3)^{26–28}. Malaria parasites of non-human primates span this zoonotic spectrum and, therefore, pose variable risks to contemporary human populations. Adaptation to the human host facilitates transition along the zoonotic spectrum. Figure adapted from Scully et al.²⁰.

Primary challenges posed to malaria eradication

Non-human primates harbor a wide diversity of malaria parasites, and our capacity to identify those that pose the greatest threat to malaria eradication is complicated by the multifaceted processes that govern zoonotic disease emergence^{1,30}. Although the increasingly widespread application of molecular diagnostics will likely reveal novel zoonotic infections that have heretofore been overlooked, this report focuses upon primate malaria parasites that have been known to be transmitted to human hosts in natural settings. In essence, this category is comprised of four parasites: *P. knowlesi*, *P. cynomolgi*, *P. simium*, and *P. brasilianum* (**Table 1**). African great apes as a potential reservoir of *P. vivax*, *P. ovale*, and *P. malariae* infection is also briefly highlighted.

As discussed in the *Background* section, malaria parasites can be arranged along the “zoonotic spectrum” by their epidemiological affinity for the human host²⁰ (**Figure 2**). Generally speaking, parasites that occupy Stage 1 of the zoonotic spectrum pose a low to non-existent threat to malaria eradication efforts, because these species are rarely (if ever) transmitted to human hosts. Humans are either rarely exposed to these species or these parasites lack the molecular machinery to replicate in human cells. By contrast, human-adapted malaria parasites that occupy Stage 3 are responsible for the vast majority of human cases globally. Although these parasites originated in primate reservoirs thousands of years ago^{6,8}, these species have since adapted to the human host and are capable of efficient (vector-borne) transmission among humans. Accordingly, these species inflict the greatest public health burden and are the primary target of malaria control efforts.

All zoonotic parasites discussed in this section occupy the intermediate stage between these two extremes. These species are capable of infecting human hosts but are incapable of sustaining long-term human-to-human transmission. It is critical to note, however, that not all parasites that occupy Stage 2 of the zoonotic spectrum pose an equal threat to malaria eradication. Three overarching considerations dictate the threat that a primate malaria parasite poses to the human population: (1) the magnitude of primate-to-human transmission, (2) the degree of parasite adaptation to the human host, and (3) the magnitude of human-to-human transmission. Each of these considerations holds important consequences for malaria eradication.

Fundamentally, the magnitude of primate-to-human transmission dictates the quantity and spatial distribution of zoonotic cases. By analyzing the component parts of the zoonotic system (e.g., the ecological drivers of transmission intensity and the geographic distribution of the primate reservoir), resources can be efficiently allocated to regions where cases of a particular parasite are most likely to arise. It is important to note that primate-to-human transmission may produce localized outbreaks, but these events will generally be confined to the geographic distribution of the animal reservoir. Although it is unlikely that such sporadic primate-to-human transmission events can be entirely eliminated, targeted public health efforts can minimize the impact of these zoonoses.

Table 1 | Zoonotic malaria parasites of non-human primates.

Parasite	Primate-to-human	Human-to-human	Threat level	Key Refs
<i>Southeast Asia</i>				
<i>P. knowlesi</i>	Yes	No? (potential <i>in vitro</i>)	High	4,5,17,21,31,32
<i>P. cynomolgi</i>	Yes	Unknown	Medium	22,23
<i>South America</i>				
<i>P. simium</i>	Yes	Unknown	High	24,33–36
<i>P. brasilianum</i>	Yes	Unknown	Medium	25,34,35,37
<i>Equatorial Africa</i>				
<i>P. vivax</i>	Yes	Unknown	Low	8,9
<i>P. ovale</i>	Unknown	Unknown	Unknown	6,11–13
<i>P. malariae</i>	Unknown	Unknown	Unknown	6,11–13

By contrast, the consequences of a zoonotic malaria parasite that is well-adapted to the human population and efficiently transmissible therein would be considerably more severe. Transmission among human hosts would enable a parasite to transcend the geographic distribution of the primate reservoir. By expanding the pool of susceptible human hosts in this manner, a malaria parasite would be capable of achieving larger outbreak sizes and possibly sustained transmission in the human population. It is conceivable that this expansion of the parasite population would beget more opportunities for adaptation, and by extension, transmission chains of progressively greater length. Accordingly, evidence of parasite adaptation or of human-to-human transmission would warrant very careful consideration in the context of malaria eradication.

This section outlines the emerging body of evidence concerning zoonotic malaria parasites in an attempt to characterize the threat that these Stage 2 parasites pose to malaria eradication efforts. It is important to note, however, that this picture is likely to change considerably as more research into primate malaria zoonoses is performed.

Southeast Asia: Old World monkey reservoirs of P. knowlesi and P. cynomolgi

Plasmodium knowlesi, a zoonotic malaria parasite of macaque monkeys, is responsible for a growing number of human cases in Southeast Asia^{4,5,32}. Although long-tailed macaques and pig-tailed macaques each harbor a high prevalence of *P. knowlesi* infection³⁸, parasites of each reservoir species appear to be reproductively isolated³². While it remains unclear whether this parasite population structure stems from geographic isolation or molecular restriction, both clades are capable of infecting human hosts³².

Long mistaken for *P. malariae* due to its morphological similarity, molecular methods have since implicated zoonotic *P. knowlesi* in up to 70% of malaria infections currently reported in rural Malaysia^{4,5}. Interestingly, efforts to eliminate *P. falciparum* and *P. vivax* in Southeast Asia have coincided with an increase in the incidence of *P. knowlesi*, an effect that cannot exclusively be explained by elevated

surveillance or improved molecular diagnosis methodology^{17,21}. Accordingly, *P. knowlesi* zoonosis constitutes a major hurdle to malaria eradication efforts in Southeast Asia and may represent a harbinger of future challenges in other geographic locations as zoonotic parasites compete to fill the host niche left by *P. falciparum* and *P. vivax*.

Although human-to-human *P. knowlesi* transmission has not been conclusively demonstrated in natural settings, this parasite produces gametocytes (i.e., transmission stages) in human blood *in vitro*, suggesting that larger outbreaks stemming from human-to-human transmission are conceivable³⁹. Additionally, *in vitro* adaptation of *P. knowlesi* to human blood has revealed that enhanced invasion of older erythrocytes enables this parasite to achieve a marked increase in the rate of proliferation in human blood^{40,41}.

Nevertheless, the current body of evidence indicates that monkey-to-human transmission is the sole route of human *P. knowlesi* infection and that outbreaks will likely be confined to the geographic distribution of the macaque reservoir. On finer-grained spatial scales, changes in patterns of land-use, such as deforestation, have been implicated as risk factors for *P. knowlesi* zoonosis³¹. Adult males working in agricultural areas appear to be particularly susceptible to infection, suggesting that behavioral factors likely play an important role in exposure, as well⁴².

Taken together, the increasing magnitude of *P. knowlesi* transmission in Southeast Asia eclipses that of any other primate malaria parasite, indicating that this parasite should not be overlooked in the context of malaria eradication efforts in this region. Although there is currently no evidence of human-to-human *P. knowlesi* transmission, *in vitro* experiments highlight the capacity for adaptation to the human host and suggests that this situation should be monitored closely as the potential for larger scale outbreaks exists.

In addition to *P. knowlesi*, another parasite of macaque monkeys—*P. cynomolgi*—has recently been isolated from human hosts in Southeast Asia. Although only a single instance of human *P. cynomolgi* infection had been recorded prior to this year²², this parasite was responsible for five documented cases in Borneo during January of 2018²³. Although little is known about the epidemiological drivers of *P. cynomolgi* zoonosis, these results may suggest that the magnitude of *P. cynomolgi* infection has been underestimated and that human encroachment into macaque habitat has begun to precipitate an increase in the incidence of these cases. More work will be necessary to evaluate the nature of this potential threat.

South America: New World monkey reservoirs of P. simium and P. brasilianum

The species richness of New World monkey malaria parasites is greatly reduced relative to that of other primates. In fact, only two endemic species—*P. simium* and *P. brasilianum*—have been isolated from New World monkeys. Heretofore, *P. simium* has been isolated from howler monkeys (*Alouatta* spp.), miquis (*Brachyteles* spp.), and capuchin monkeys (*Cebus* spp., *Sapajus* spp.)^{34,36,43}. *Plasmodium brasilianum* has also been isolated from a wide range of New World monkey hosts^{34,37}. Future work will be necessary to

comprehensively quantify the prevalence and distribution of these parasites within New World monkey reservoirs. However, the current body of evidence suggests that *P. simium* is confined to the Atlantic Forest region in South and Southeastern Brazil^{24,35}, while *P. brasilianum* is more geographically widespread within South America^{34,35,37,44}.

Phylogenetic analyses have revealed that *P. simium* is very closely related to *P. vivax*, while *P. brasilianum* is a close relative of *P. malariae* (**Figure 1**). Interestingly, patterns of phylogenetic clustering and genetic diversity suggest that each of these parasites likely emerged in New World monkey populations less than 500 years ago, the result of human-to-monkey cross-species transmission events^{16,45–47}. Now that these species have adapted to New World monkeys, a key question concerns whether these species have retained the capacity for human infection and forward transmission in human populations.

Despite limited sampling, both *P. simium* and *P. brasilianum* have now been isolated from human hosts^{24,25,33}. Because *P. simium* and *P. brasilianum* are nearly morphologically indistinguishable from their human-adapted relatives, it is likely that the magnitude of monkey-to-human transmission of these parasites has been underestimated by virtue of misdiagnosis. Indeed, Brasil *et al.*²⁴ recently used a molecular assay to demonstrate that outbreaks of presumed *P. vivax* in the Atlantic Forest region of Rio de Janeiro state, Brazil—where elimination had been achieved for over 50 years—are actually attributable to *P. simium*.

If zoonotic *P. simium* and *P. brasilianum* outbreaks are generalizable to regions beyond Brazil^{24,33–35,37}, surveillance of New World monkey reservoirs will be an integral component of malaria control efforts in throughout South America. It will, therefore, be of central importance to invest in molecular epidemiological studies that quantify rates of zoonotic exposure and transmission in these regions to thoroughly quantify the magnitude of this underappreciated threat. It should also be noted that *P. falciparum* has been isolated from wild New World monkeys (the result of human-to-monkey transmission events)³⁷, and *P. falciparum* (as well as *P. vivax*) is capable of producing gametocytes in captive, splenectomized *Aotus* monkeys, an important model system for studies of this parasite⁴⁸. These results suggest that New World monkeys could constitute a reservoir of human *P. falciparum* infection.

Given its close similarity to *P. vivax*, it will also be necessary to monitor whether *P. simium* harbors the potential for transmission among human hosts. Brasil *et al.*²⁴ reported that most individuals who acquired *P. simium* infection had visited the Atlantic Forest region, where exposure to vectors of New World monkey parasites likely occurred. However, a subset of individuals that tested positive for *P. simium* did not report travelling to this region, indicating that follow-up work will be necessary to evaluate the capacity for transmission among humans.

Equatorial Africa: African great ape reservoirs of P. vivax, P. malariae, and P. ovale

African great apes harbor a wide diversity of malaria parasites, including representatives closely related

to all four human-adapted parasite species. Although ape relatives of *P. falciparum* (sub-genus *Laverania*) appear to be highly host-restricted^{6,49} (**Figure 1**), there is growing evidence that *P. vivax*, *P. malariae*, and *P. ovale* possess the capacity cross species barriers more promiscuously. Given that malaria parasites are highly prevalent in African great ape populations⁶ and mosquito vectors of these parasites readily bite humans⁵⁰, it is likely that human exposure occurs with regularity in parts of equatorial Africa. Accordingly, African great ape reservoirs deserve a special degree of consideration in the context of malaria eradication.

Once believed to have emerged from macaque monkeys^{51,52}, improved sampling of non-human primates has revealed that the human *P. vivax* pandemic actually originated in African great ape reservoirs tens of thousands of years ago⁸. Human *P. vivax* isolates form a monophyletic clade embedded within the diversity of closely related ape parasites, suggesting that little cross-species transmission occurs on contemporary timescales. However, ape-to-human transmission has recently been documented in a Caucasian traveler who spent 18 days working in a forest in the Central African Republic⁹, suggesting that high frequencies of Duffy-negativity in equatorial African populations (>95% allele frequency in some regions⁵³) may be a primary barrier to zoonotic *P. vivax* transmission.

Nevertheless, reports of *P. vivax* outbreaks in equatorial Africa are striking⁵⁴. Although expression of the Duffy Antigen/Receptor for Chemokines (DARC) receptor has long been thought to be an essential determinant of *P. vivax* erythrocyte invasion^{55,56}, evidence of Duffy-negative erythrocyte invasion has begun to accumulate during the last decade⁵⁷⁻⁶², and several recent studies conducted in countries harboring African great apes have isolated *P. vivax* from Duffy-negative individuals^{60,63,64}. While very preliminary, these emerging trends suggest that African populations may harbor greater susceptibility to zoonotic *P. vivax* parasites than had previously been acknowledged.

Additional sampling has demonstrated that African great apes also harbor *P. malariae* and *P. ovale*^{6,11-13} parasites. Very little research has been conducted on *P. malariae* and *P. ovale* infections of ape hosts, and three currently untested hypotheses could explain the isolation of these parasites from both human and African great ape hosts. First, it is possible that human infections are, indeed, the result of ancient and/or contemporary zoonoses of ape origin. In this scenario, malaria control efforts should carefully consider the ape reservoir as a potential source of ongoing human *P. malariae* and *P. ovale* infection. Second, it is conceivable that these ape infections are anthroponotic (i.e., transmitted from human to ape). Given that anthroponotic pathogens constitute a major source of mortality among wild apes⁶⁵⁻⁶⁷, this finding would hold significant relevance to the conservation of these endangered primates. Third, it is possible that some *P. malariae* and *P. ovale* strains hold the capacity for promiscuous transmission among humans and apes. This possibility represents a ‘worst-case scenario,’ and would warrant consideration by both the public health and wildlife conservation communities.

The public health community has largely overlooked *P. ovale* and *P. malariae* due to the relative

obscurity of these parasites. However, as efforts to control *P. falciparum* and *P. vivax* inch closer to regional elimination, these neglected tropical diseases may begin to factor more prominently into policy discussions. The recent sequencing of the *P. ovale* and *P. malariae* genomes constitutes an important first step in understanding the biology of these parasites⁶⁸. Inference of the magnitude of ape-to-human transmission will be necessary to further elucidate the epidemiological dynamics of these parasites.

Recommended Course of Action

Previous sections described the threat that primate malaria parasites pose to malaria eradication efforts. Outlined below are a series of recommendations that should be taken to minimize the potential impact of these zoonoses on human populations. Fundamentally, it will be critical that scientific and public health resources be invested in activities that serve to (1) evaluate the threat that primate malaria parasites pose to human populations, and (2) mitigate the threat that primate malaria parasites pose to eradication efforts.

1. Evaluate the threat that primate malaria parasites pose to human populations

Recent research has demonstrated that a handful of primate malaria parasites pose a tangible risk to human populations in Southeast Asia, South America, and equatorial Africa. However, most research into malaria zoonoses is in its infancy, and molecular diagnostics are likely to reveal additional zoonotic parasites that are capable of infecting human hosts in the future. Accordingly, it will be necessary to invest in basic scientific research that critically evaluates the ecological, epidemiological, and molecular drivers of primate malaria zoonoses. Doing so will facilitate the identification of exactly which parasites pose a tangible threat to human populations, where these parasites are distributed, and when seasonal cases are most likely to occur. To elucidate these topics, we must (1) identify foci of human exposure to zoonotic parasites, (2) evaluate the frequency of primate-to-human transmission, and (3) discern evidence of simian parasite adaptation to the human host.

1.1 Identify foci of human exposure to zoonotic parasites

The probability of primate-to-human transmission depends, in part, upon the magnitude of human exposure to the zoonotic parasite. Accordingly, environmental factors that mediate spatiotemporal variation in human exposure will tend to influence where and when a given parasite is likely to emerge. This information can be operationalized to identify hypothetical zoonotic transmission hotspots and design emerging infectious disease surveillance efforts^{27,69}.

Variation in exposure to zoonotic malaria parasites is structured by three parameters: (1) the incidence

of infection in the primate reservoir, (2) vector biting preferences, and (3) spatial overlap between human and reservoir hosts. Fundamentally, zoonotic exposure is most likely to occur where humans live in close proximity to primates that harbor a high incidence of malaria infection, which is transmitted by *Anopheline* vectors that bite both humans and primates promiscuously.

The capacity to identify these exposure hotspots will require dedicated efforts to sample all components of the zoonotic system—from primate reservoir to mosquito to human host. For a given parasite of interest, studies of entomological inoculation rates (via sampling and analysis of parasite rates in *Anopheles* mosquito vectors) and serological measures of exposure (via longitudinal sampling of human populations) in multiple transmission settings will offer direct estimates of zoonotic exposure. Emphasis on vector surveillance will also play a key role in elucidating the biting preferences of Anopheline vectors, as well as their capacity to transmit both human-adapted and zoonotic parasites.

Given the diverse nature of these studies, it will be important to leverage the research infrastructure established by field biologists, ecologists, and primatologists by forming mutually beneficial partnerships with long-term biological field sites, many of which—like the Kibale Chimpanzee Project (western Uganda)—have been operational for decades. Wild primate populations can act as sentinels for emerging infectious diseases^{16,70}, and the capacity to sample primate populations longitudinally offers the opportunity to identify trends in pathogen incidence relative to factors such as climatic variation or land-use change. By incentivizing field sites to participate in disease surveillance programs, public health organizations can leverage the expertise and infrastructure that these studies have cultivated over decades of biological field research.

1.2 Evaluate the frequency of primate-to-human transmission

Because molecular factors at the human-parasite interface may form additional barriers to cross-species transmission, evidence of elevated exposure to a primate malaria parasite is insufficient to predict zoonotic emergence. Once human exposure to a particular parasite has been demonstrated, it will also be necessary to evaluate the frequency of primate-to-human transmission. This goal can be accomplished by conducting epidemiological surveys of human populations in predicted exposure hotspots. Critically, these efforts should employ the most sensitive molecular diagnostics available, because the morphology of many primate malaria parasites is nearly indistinguishable from that of human-adapted parasites. Additionally, due to the infrequent nature of primate-to-human transmission, these zoonotic disease surveillance efforts should prioritize individuals that exhibit a high risk of exposure (e.g., individuals that frequently visit or work in forests harboring primate reservoirs). Resources can be efficiently allocated by focusing particularly upon predicted exposure hotspots. It will also be necessary to standardize and strengthen the investigation and reporting of primate malaria cases in order to facilitate timely responses from the public health community.

1.3 Discern evidence of simian parasite adaptation to the human host

While sporadic primate-to-human transmission events may complicate malaria eradication efforts, infections that are not efficiently transmissible among human hosts will generally produce localized transmission chains that are confined to the geographic distribution of the primate reservoir. However, subsequent parasite adaptation holds the potential to amplify either the efficiency of parasite replication within the human host or the magnitude of transmission among humans, potentially resulting in outbreaks of greater public health impact.

Although all stages of the complex *Plasmodium* lifecycle² offer opportunities for molecular incompatibility—and, by extension, opportunities for adaptation to the human host—most research concerning the host-specificity of primate malaria parasites has focused upon host-parasite interactions occurring in the context of the red blood cell²⁰. However, species barriers to liver stage infection and molecular incompatibilities between parasite and mosquito vector constitute important avenues for future research. In particular, evidence that a zoonotic parasite is capable of developing gametocytes (i.e., transmission stages) in the human host constitutes an important indicator of a parasite's potential for transmission within the human host population.

It will be critical that researchers develop *in vitro* culture systems for high-risk malaria parasites (e.g., *P. knowlesi*, *P. simium*) that span all elements of the *Plasmodium* lifecycle—namely blood stage, liver stage, and mosquito stage. *In vitro* adaptation experiments will reveal key pathways by which primate malaria parasites adapt to the human cellular environment (e.g., duplication of the *P. knowlesi* Duffy Binding Protein-alpha^{40,41}). Once these pathways have been identified, molecular epidemiologists will be able to screen parasite isolates for genetic signatures of adaptation and quantify their frequency and geographic distribution. These data could be coupled with molecular and phylogenetic estimates of human-to-human transmission over time in order to estimate the risk of larger scale emergence. Additionally, evidence of gametocyte development should be monitored particularly closely, both *in vitro* and in natural settings, in order to infer transmission potential.

2. Mitigate the threat that primate malaria parasites pose to eradication efforts

Although future scientific research will be necessary to more systematically quantify the threat that malaria zoonoses pose to human populations, the emerging body of evidence suggests that several parasites are worthy of special consideration in the context of malaria eradication (**Table 1**). In particular, two zoonotic systems offer important case studies: the macaque parasite, *P. knowlesi* (peninsular Malaysia and Borneo), and the New World monkey parasite, *P. simium* (Atlantic Forest region, Brazil). While incidence of the former has been increasing during the last decade (possibly as an unintended byproduct of malaria control efforts^{17,21}), the latter has recently emerged to produce an outbreak in a region where elimination

had been achieved over 50 years ago²⁴. While efforts to map the spatiotemporal distribution of these parasites will facilitate more fine-grained resource allocation to particular foci of transmission, several courses of action should be taken to reduce the impact of these zoonoses moving forward. In particular, it will be important to invest in activities that (1) improve the diagnosis of simian malaria parasites, (2) evaluate the efficacy of current malaria therapies when applied to simian malaria parasites, (3) intensify control activities in zoonotic foci to reduce the risk of human-to-human transmission, and (4) promote advocacy and education to raise awareness among stakeholders ranging from public health officials to local populations impacted by these pathogens.

2.1 Improve diagnosis of simian malaria parasites

The capacity to discern evidence of primate-to-human transmission relies upon the development and application of diagnostics that are both sensitive and specific to the parasite of interest. First, it will be critical to develop and/or improve existing rapid diagnostic tests (RDTs) for high-risk primate malaria parasites (e.g., *P. knowlesi*, *P. simium*). Public health workers must seek to preserve positive blood samples to facilitate the development and evaluation of these assays. Application of such RDTs will enable the healthcare system to maximize the breadth of surveillance efforts in a cost-effective manner.

However, given that some primate malaria parasites are very closely related to those that circulate in human populations (e.g., *P. simium* diverged from *P. vivax* <500 years ago and has retained very high homology to the latter), RDTs may not permit adequate discrimination between human and zoonotic parasites. Accordingly, it will be equally important for researchers to use molecular diagnostics in order to confirm positive RDTs. For example, de Alvarenga et al.⁷¹ developed a genetic assay that allows for discrimination between *P. simium* and *P. vivax* via genotyping of a single diagnostic mitochondrial polymorphism. Though more technologically demanding, molecular diagnostics will minimize false negatives and reduce misdiagnosis of zoonotic infections. To achieve these goals, we should promote the development of reliable and comparable molecular-based zoonotic malaria diagnosis through support to relevant laboratories, such as those participating in the WHO malaria NAAT EQA scheme.

However, because many molecular diagnostic assays employ reagents that require a cold chain, their application may not be locally feasible in rural areas where zoonotic transmission is most likely to occur. Thus, it will be important to design standardized protocols for the collection, characterization, storage, and exportation of blood samples from individuals of confirmed or suspected infection status. Ideally, these protocols will take advantage of reagents that reduce the rate of nucleic acid degradation at room temperature. If possible, diagnostic infrastructure should also be augmented in zoonotic exposure hotspots (e.g., via investment in field-deployable thermocyclers for PCR-based assays).

In addition to the molecular diagnostic tools discussed above, we should also seek to develop and apply

tools that assay the complexity of infection within hosts more comprehensively. The elevated parasitemia of human-adapted malaria parasites, such as *P. falciparum*, may mask the signal of simian parasites that inefficiently invade human cells. While the low parasitemia of the latter may reduce pathogenicity, these subclinical infections present opportunities for adaptation of the zoonotic parasite to the human host. Accordingly, it will be critical that surveys seeking to uncover evidence of primate-to-human transmission use next generation sequencing methods that more comprehensively sample the richness of parasite species within a host. It will also be important to minimize other sources of sampling bias (e.g., by conducting surveys of asymptomatic hosts, as well as clinical cases).

2.2 *Evaluate the efficacy of current malaria therapies when applied to simian malaria parasites*

Once evidence of cross-species transmission has been established (see *Section 1.2*), anti-malarial drugs must be employed to treat patients. Even if cases are asymptomatic, administration of treatment will minimize opportunities for parasite adaptation to the human cellular environment and reduce the potential for forward transmission. It will be important to test the efficacy of currently available anti-malarial treatments *in vitro* once model systems are established.

The identification of clinical cases will also provide opportunities for validation of treatment efficacy *in vivo*. In geographic regions that harbor the potential for zoonotic transmission, malaria control efforts should emphasize enhanced surveillance with a focus on species identification at point-of-care. If primate malaria-specific RDTs are developed, healthcare workers will be able to identify cases, record treatment outcomes, and report results in real-time. In cases in which zoonotic infection is recognized only retrospectively, treatment outcomes should be aggregated and recorded *a posteriori* for subsequent evaluation of treatment outcomes.

2.3 *Intensify the control activities in zoonotic foci to reduce risk of human-to-human transmission*

Following the identification of zoonotic exposure foci (see *Section 1.1*), it will be critical to intensify control efforts in these areas in order to reduce opportunities for parasite adaptation to the human host and limit the potential for human-to-human parasite transmission. Much of the discussion above has focused on idiosyncratic elements of the zoonotic system (e.g., vector biting preferences, transmission dynamics in the primate reservoir, patterns of human encroachment into primate habitat). Once an exposure hotspot has been identified, however, efforts to combat primate zoonoses can maximize efficiency by leveraging the infrastructure and interventions developed to control human malaria parasites.

In particular, the implementation of vector control strategies designed to reduce the incidence of human-adapted malaria parasites can be co-opted to minimize the burden of malaria zoonoses. First, the distribution of long-lasting insecticide-treated bed nets (LLINs) and the administration of indoor residual

spraying (IRS) should be a key component of the response. These interventions should be distributed at high coverage among populations living in close proximity to primate hosts harboring the zoonotic parasite of interest (e.g., rural Southeast Asian villages living beside populations of macaque monkeys harboring *P. knowlesi*). Following WHO guidance, in most circumstances, control efforts should maximize administration of either LLINs or IRS, rather than a combination thereof. In some cases, larvicidal treatment of aquatic mosquito habitat may also constitute a viable control measure. However, this intervention should only be administered as a secondary precaution once LLINs or IRS has been sufficiently implemented and only when a comprehensive understanding of the aquatic habitat of vector species has been cultivated. For individuals or populations at particularly high risk of exposure (e.g., those living in very close proximity to primate hosts or permanent vector aquatic habitats), personal protective measures may also be warranted. Simultaneously, active surveillance of vector populations will be necessary to monitor the magnitude of ongoing zoonotic transmission in response to these control measures.

In addition to vector control strategies, early diagnosis of infection and prompt treatment will also likely pay dividends in reducing the burden of malaria zoonoses. Expanded access to rapid diagnostic tests and treatment options will limit opportunities for adaptation to the human host. Accordingly, it is particularly important that the public health apparatus intensify malaria control activities in predicted zoonotic exposure hotspots.

2.4 Advocacy and education

Finally, in order to effectively implement these recommendations, we must participate in activities that raise awareness of the threat that cryptic zoonotic parasites pose to human populations. This recommendation is underscored by the growing burdens posed by *P. knowlesi* in Malaysia (long misdiagnosed as *P. malariae*) and *P. simium* in Brazil (frequently misdiagnosed as *P. vivax*). Until healthcare professionals living in transmission foci are briefed on the nature of these threats and better diagnostic tools are developed to identify them, primate malaria parasites will continue to be mistaken for their human-adapted cousins. Such misdiagnoses will lead to inefficient resource allocation and suboptimal health outcomes. Further, it will be critical to engage at-risk populations to ensure the consistent and effective application of preventative measures. Only through the collaboration of a diversity of stakeholders ranging from policymakers and NGOs to healthcare professionals and local communities can we endeavor to combat this emerging threat to public health.

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